

Design of a Natural Circulation Experiment to Investigate Flow Stability

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ABSTRACT

A numerical methodology for the study of the stability characteristics of natural circulation systems using molten salts as working fluid is currently under development. This numerical methodology is intended as an aid tool for the design of passive decay heat removal systems for Molten Salt Reactors (MSRs). This paper presents the design of a natural circulation experiment that will be used to test this novel numerical methodology. The experiment has been designed to obtain 2D-like Rayleigh-Bénard cells with laminar flow. Moreover, the experiment will allow to obtain flow conditions close to those encountered in a natural convection system with an internal heat source. As the focus of the methodology is placed on its capability to accurately describe the dynamic behavior of the system, the experiment has been designed to cover a significant range of operational conditions (Rayleigh number) and to obtain distinguishable flow states and the transitions between them. The experiment design robustness has been investigated by performing numerical studies considering various potential bias and uncertainties. In the presented case the principal bias and uncertainties are related to the heating and cooling mechanisms, the wall materials effects and the possible non-negligible interaction with the environment. Results from this study show that an experimental configuration using a flat-cavity geometry will provide meaningful results and a sufficiently complex behavior for testing the methodology without resorting to a system with a turbulent or highly 3D dynamic. Finally, the experiment can operate with a conventional fluid while retaining key phenomena specific to the molten salts.

KEYWORDS

Natural circulation, molten salt reactor, experimental design

1. INTRODUCTION

In recent years, advances in the nuclear industry have been made regarding the development of some of the novel GEN-IV nuclear reactor designs [1,2]. In the particular case of the Molten Salt Reactor (MSR), one of the current challenges is to gain a deeper understanding of the dynamic behavior of the salt, given the particular conditions of this design, combining very high operational temperatures, a non-conventional working fluid and a circulating nuclear fuel.

For the design of the different systems comprised in an MSR, it is of utmost importance to count with a numerical tool capable of including the underlying complexity of the dynamic of the circulating salt. In particular, for the case of some passive safety systems, an additional layer of complexity needs to be taken into account. Indeed, the systems based on natural circulation have a behavior that can be heavily influenced by the specific phenomena of the molten salt, as being radiative heat transfer, the presence of an internally distributed heat source [3] and phase change.

For a proper understanding of the dynamic of a natural circulation system and its consequent design, new models, simulations and dedicated experiments need to be carried out; despite of involving a series of different phenomena that has been thoroughly studied in the past, the current knowledge is significantly biased towards cases where these effects act separately and the consequence of its simultaneous interaction is not properly represented.

A new numerical methodology is currently under development to assess this shortfall, but to verify its capability for describing the problem at stake, experimental data is needed to support it. The work presented here focuses on the design of a natural circulation experiment whose expected results are sufficient to provide meaningful conclusions about both the understanding of the underlying phenomena and the performance and accuracy of the developed numerical model.

A major factor to consider in these natural circulation systems is its passive behavior [4], this is, they are designed to fulfill its function without an active control action, but only through the behavior driven by its natural response. This characteristic makes the system very reliable, as long as there exist an accurate understanding of its underlying behavior. One of the factors required to ensure this reliability resides in the stability of the system; in front of an event where the system suffers a deviation from its operational conditions, the natural response should ensure that the dynamic is not heavily affected and its function is not compromised.

2. EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

2.1. Experiment Requirements

For the experimental design a series of requirements need to be covered to ensure that the expected results are sufficient to provide meaningful conclusions about both the understanding of the underlying phenomena and the performance and accuracy of the developed numerical model.

Firstly, a laminar flow is preferred since it would allow to concentrate the focus in the aspects of interest; a dynamic behavior that exhibits a high degree of turbulence or a highly 3-dimensional flow is not desired both for modeling reasons, since it due to the current state of development of the numerical tool it would significantly increase the modeling effort and for experimental reasons since it would increase the uncertainty of measurements and the capability to discern between different dynamic states.

Secondly, one of the main focuses of the numerical tool is to correctly describe the dynamic states of the system, which includes the capability to identify transitions between different states and the surge of instability effects. For an experimental campaign to produce significant results to aid the validation of these capabilities the behavior of the system should exhibit a sufficiently large number of different states, where the transition and the rise of instabilities is discernible.

Another important aspect to be captured in the experimental campaign would be the inclusion of molten salt specific phenomena. Among those already mentioned, the internal volumetric heat source would constitute one of the main drivers for the natural circulation and thus an important phenomenon. Some of the other effects could be attempted to be included, as being the solidification of the salt or a non-negligible radiative heat transfer mechanism, but these more case-dependent phenomena, while the distributed heat source is an unavoidable effect.

For a proper characterization of the dynamic states expected to be obtained, methods capable of flow field measurements are preferred, such as optical methods as being Particle Image Velocimetry (PIV), where the velocity field can be measured in a 2D plane simultaneously. Point measurements of other thermodynamic variables as temperature or pressure could prove to be useful and, in some cases necessary, but more inferring might be necessary and not even a qualitative description could be obtained without intermediary processing of the measurements.

Finally, since the detection of the transition between different states is meant to be accurately distinguishable, it is necessary to ensure a proper control over the boundary conditions of the system, such as heat losses, temperature over the walls or nonuniformities since this can significantly affect the behavior of the system and the conditions for which a change occurs. In the case where this deviations from an ideal case are unavoidable, a prior study and an understanding on how these effects affect the system is required.

2.2. Configuration Selection

Based on the experiment requirements and previous numerical studies both from the literature and related to this work [5-7], a configuration based on the Rayleigh-Bénard convection case was selected for the experiment. This configuration comprises a series of characteristic to ensure that the expected results serve the purposes of validation of the numerical model.

The geometry of the system consists in a 3D rectangular cavity similar to the Rayleigh-Bénard convection case, this is, a body of fluid heated and cooled from the bottom and top surfaces respectively, while the side walls remain insulated from the surrounding, as shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1. Sketch of a Rayleigh-Bénard convection configuration.

Additionally, the system is previewed to have an alternative work condition, where the bottom surface is also insulated and the heat source is shifted to a constant heat flux in the back wall. The main characteristic of the chosen configuration for this design is the flattened geometry in one of the directions, resulting in 2D-like geometry. As it will be shown in the following section, this feature serves a number of purposes, starting in delaying the onset of turbulence and avoiding highly 3D behavior while working within the laminar regime, secondly it has been investigated that a small thickness allows to emulate a distributed volumetric heat through the distributed heat input at the walls, allowing to capture one the molten salt specific phenomena without the need to resort to an experiment using nuclear material. Finally, the resulting flow patterns are strongly governed by a planar dynamic, this is, the velocity component in the depth dimension is negligible against the other two directions, which results particularly useful to characterize the dynamic of the system through methods as PIV; measuring the velocity field in a single plane would allow to characterize, at least qualitatively, the flow pattern of the whole cavity, without requiring to characterize the dependency of the flow pattern in the depth direction.

With respect of the constructive aspect of this design, the use of transparent materials and conventional fluids (near room temperature conditions) is envisioned. This is in line with the use of PIV methods for the characterization of the system; a conventional fluid would not require high temperatures, hence reducing the amount of insulation required to avoid significant heat losses, which combined with using transparent structural materials would allow for the direct visualization of the dynamic of the fluid.

This experimental design would accept the use of different conventional working fluids, resulting in the coverage of a wider range of thermodynamic conditions, namely the Rayleigh number, while using a fixed geometry, hence allowing to study different conditions and obtain a more extensive set of dynamic states to use for validation. For compatibility with the use of transparent structural materials and optical methods for measurements, the use of transparent liquids is envisioned.

The proposed design is shown in Fig. 2, the flat cavity geometry. The temperatures at the bottom and top walls can be fixed by a water cooling system. The lateral walls of the cavity are made of PMMA (Polymethyl methacrylate) and the bottom and top walls on copper for a more even temperature distribution. The whole setup operates at nearly room temperatures. The use of a flat cavity allows increasing the viscous effects and thus to maintain a laminar flow conditions while the Rayleigh number is increased to obtain different states in the natural circulation system. The flat cavity setup is also well suited to perform PIV measurements and also, in certain conditions, to simulate a volumetric heat source by a heat input in one of the lateral walls, as will be addressed in section 3.3.

Figure 2. Sketch of the proposed configuration for initial experimental design.

3. NUMERICAL STUDIES

The initial design is based on preliminary results from the literature and numerical simulations [5-7], that demonstrate the presence of the phenomena of interest, this is, a dynamic behavior in natural circulation that exhibits a large set of different flow patterns within the laminar regime. In the Rayleigh-Bénard convection case the main dimensionless parameters that govern the dynamic of the system, are the physical parameter, the Rayleigh number (Ra), shown in Equation 1, which is an analogy to the Reynolds number for natural convection cases and the geometric parameter, the Aspect ratio (A), that refers to the ratio between the height and the width of the system.

$$Ra = \frac{g\beta\Delta TL^3Pr}{\nu^2} \quad (1)$$

where g is the gravity acceleration, β is the thermal expansion coefficient, ΔT is the temperature difference between the plates, L is the characteristic dimension of the system, in this case the height, Pr is the Prandtl number and ν is the kinematic viscosity. For cases where the boundary condition is a fixed heat flux instead of fixed temperature, there is an analogous definition for Ra, shown in Equation 2.

$$Ra = \frac{g\beta q'' L^4 Pr}{\nu^2 k} \quad (2)$$

where q'' stands for the heat flux and k for the thermal conductivity of the fluid.

From a previous study [7], the behavior of this system has been investigated within a range of both dimensionless parameters to describe its dynamic within the laminar regime, as is summarized in Fig. 3. The starting point beyond the stagnation condition corresponds to a single circulation cell covering the whole cavity. The different flow patterns are shown but ranges with coexisting solutions are omitted for the sake of simplicity.

Figure 3 – Simplified bifurcation diagram of a Rayleigh-Bénard convection case. Numerical solutions are obtained for the studied range of parameters. The flow patterns are shown to illustrate the evolution of the dynamic of the system.

For values of A larger than one, the geometry allows the allocation of a larger number of smaller circulation cells. While the value of Ra increases, the intensity of these cells increases accordingly until at a given

value the system begins to show an oscillating behavior in the relative intensity of the cells. Furthermore, the behavior of the system shifts to a dynamic where cells arise from the corners and merge in the center of the cavity. Finally, other dynamic states are achievable for larger values of A and Ra , where the number of cells increases but the mechanisms are similar: a constant number of cells with either a steady or oscillating asymptotic behavior or a cell merging mechanism.

Once the behavior of the system is known, the next step is to verify that such a configuration taken from a simplified numerical case can be achieved in a real experiment, while retaining the phenomena of interest. This must take into account that most of the boundary conditions of the system will differ from an idealized case and inhomogeneities and oscillations are expected, while also considering a set of limitations such as availability of working fluid and structural materials, feasible dimensions and compatibility with measurement methods.

3.1. Boundary Conditions

The first stage of the numerical studies carried out in this work was to investigate the response of the system to non-idealized boundary conditions. As the proposed system has cavity-like geometry, the enforcement of boundary conditions over the velocity and pressure is achievable in a straightforward manner, whereas with the temperature conditions as being adiabatic walls and constant and uniform temperature are obtainable in an experimental setup just up to a limited degree.

Starting from the Rayleigh-Bénard convection case, a series of alternative variants were studied, where deviations from the simplified BCs are gradually introduced to investigate how the dynamic of the system is affected, in order to check if the resulting behavior continues to be adequate for an experimental study case. Fig. 4 summarizes the different flow patterns that can be obtained for in the range within the laminar regime, for an aspect ratio of $A = 2.5$. The dynamic starts from the single circulation cell, an increasing number of cells can be obtained, both in a steady-state conditions or with a periodicity in the relative intensity of the cells. Finally, some cases exhibit an oscillating behavior where the cells are continuously arising from the boundaries and merging in the center region of the cavity.

Figure 4. Velocity flow patterns obtained for a Rayleigh-Bénard convection case in a cavity geometry, within the range of laminar regime for an aspect ratio of $A=2.5$. The flow patterns are shown in order of appearance for increasing values of Ra number. a) one circulation cell, b) two circulation cells, c) one-to-three circulation cells, d) three circulation cells, e) two-to-four circulation cells. Cases b) and d) exhibit both steady and oscillating behaviors.

Once the behavior of the simplified case, the effect of introducing disturbances in the boundary conditions was studied. A parametric study was carried, considering non-uniform temperature profiles, non-adiabatic

conditions and temperature gradient due to the wall materials. In Table I, the studied variations are described together with the idealized case, showing which of the boundary conditions were modified.

Table I. Description of the studied configurations, starting from the standard Rayleigh-Bénard case.

Configuration	Top surface	Bottom surface	Front and back walls	Side walls
Standard RB	Uniform Tc	Uniform Th	Adiabatic	Adiabatic
Conductive RB	Uniform Tc	Uniform Th	Adiabatic	Conductive (linear profile between Tc and Th)
Heterogeneous RB	Non-uniform – Average Tc	Non-uniform – Average Th	Adiabatic	Adiabatic
External source RB	Uniform Tc	Uniform Th	Uniform heat flux towards the system	Adiabatic
External sink RB	Uniform Tc	Uniform Th	Uniform heat flux away from the system	Adiabatic

Once the new cases are defined, numerical simulations are carried out to study the resulting dynamic and how the initial flow patterns are affected. The results are summarized in Table II. Some flow patterns are not achievable in some of the studied configurations, while many flow patterns retain its general behavior with some slight variations over the shape or the intensity of the circulation cell, or the periodicity of its oscillating behavior.

Table II. Effect of the different configurations on the flow patterns from the standard case.

Configuration	1 Cell	2 Cells	1-3 Cells	3 Cells	2-4 Cells
Standard RB	✓	Steady - ✓ Oscillatory - ✓	✓	Steady - ✓ Oscillatory - ✓	✓
Conductive RB	Disturbed - ✓	Steady - X Oscillatory - X	Disturbed - ✓	Steady - X Oscillatory - X	-
Heterogeneous RB	Disturbed - ✓	Steady - X Oscillatory - ✓ (Disturbed)	Disturbed - ✓	Steady - X Oscillatory - ✓ (Disturbed)	X – Localized Disturbance
External source RB	Disturbed - ✓	Steady - X Oscillatory - ✓ (Disturbed)	Disturbed - ✓	Steady - X Oscillatory - ✓ (Disturbed)	Disturbed - ✓
External sink RB	Disturbed - ✓	Steady - X Oscillatory - ✓ (Disturbed)	Disturbed - ✓	Steady - X Oscillatory - ✓ (Disturbed)	Disturbed - ✓

The obtained results show that while in certain configurations some of the flow patterns are no longer achievable, most of the dynamic behavior of the system is retained at some extent, maintaining the main characteristic of this configuration being the rich dynamic in a simple system. This study also serves to point out which are important conditions that has to be enforced in the experiment design to reduce the impact of sources of uncertainty on the behavior under study.

3.2. Flat Geometry

Having selected the Rayleigh-Bénard configuration as feasible in terms of occurring phenomenology, the following step is to ensure that the conditions of this system are feasible in an experiment in terms of constructive limitations. To obtain a system working with a conventional fluid and realistic dimensions, provisions need to be taken to be able to work within laminar flow conditions. Additionally, the results previously presented are more typical of a 2D geometry, while a 3D cube shaped cavity would shift its dynamic to exhibit a different much more complex behavior [8]. To solve both of these constraints the system is chosen to have a flat cavity geometry, this is, while the height and width of the configuration are similar in dimension, the depth is smaller by an order of magnitude. Numerical simulations were carried out to demonstrate this 2D-like behavior in a 3D system under these considerations.

3.3. Distributed Heat Source

As one of the main focus of this work is to produce dedicated data for its application in molten salt systems, the experiment needs to address the specific characteristic of this type of fluid. In an experimental context, the capability of introducing an internally distributed heat source is challenging due to the complexity to replicate the conditions on a nuclear reactor. With the proposed geometry, a mindful selection of the dimensions of the system would allow to emulate the internally distributed heat source through a controlled heat flux in the walls of the system.

As previously mentioned, the flat-cavity geometry would aid with number of constraints to achieve a configuration that properly exhibits the studied behavior. Additionally, numerical studies were carried using this geometry to show the parallelism between the behavior obtained with a heat source internally distributed and one distributed as a heat flux in the boundary of the system, namely the front and/or back walls. A high degree of resemblance, dependent on the relative thickness of the cavity, was found between both cases, showing that within certain constraints, a configuration using an external heat source could effectively represent the behavior from one with an internal source. In Fig. 5 the flow patterns for both cases are shown, for a case where the depth is kept an order of magnitude smaller than the height of the cavity. A very good agreement can be noticed, with a difference in the maximum values in the order of 1%.

It is important to notice that these configurations are effectively replacing the heat source in the bottom surface of the cavity as is the Rayleigh-Bénard standard case, hence a different dynamic is obtained while maintaining the provisions of interest. In the case shown in Fig. 5 the flow pattern is the equivalent to the single convection cell case from the standard Rayleigh-Bénard.

Figure 5. Velocity flow patterns obtained for the cases of a) internal and b) surface heat source for the flat cavity configuration, for an aspect ratio of $A=2.5$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

The experimental design of a natural convection configuration has been carried out, to obtain a thermal-hydraulic system that allows to extend the understanding of the dynamic behavior of passive systems using molten salts for nuclear applications. The experiment is meant to complement previous work related to the development of a numerical methodology for the study of these type of systems [7], as a study case that exhibit results that can be used for a performance verification and validation of the methodology.

A configuration based in the Rayleigh-Bénard convection case has been selected, based on the desired dynamic behavior of the system and a series of constraints regarding the limitations encountered in a real-life application. Starting from a simplified 2D case, numerical studies have been carried out to demonstrate that despite some of the conditions of the standard case would be compromised in an experimental context, enough provisions could be taken to obtain a system where the phenomena of interest is still retained.

A preliminary design has been drawn, taken into account experimental constraints such as working fluids and structural materials, power provision mechanisms, data acquisition methods and constructive limitations regarding the dimensions of the system. While the design process presented in this work was able to produce a preliminary design, further studies are currently undergoing to consider other factors that could compromise the performance of the system. Additionally, is important to mention that the cases addressed in this work do not cover the highly 3D behavior expected in MSR applications, which is left for further studies.

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